

NEP 2020 AND TEACHER PREPARATION FOR INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

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Abstract

This article focuses on NEP2020 and Teacher education in context to Inclusive Education. It covers the key points are NEP 2020 and its importance, inclusive education, teacher education and digital era and need of digitalization of course content. The national educational policy 2020 emphasizes the importance of inclusive education and role of teacher. Here some key points related to pre - service teacher preparation is discussed in the light of NEP2020. NEP2020 recommended so many things and also provides remarkable implications for teacher preparation programs. Some of the key implications include, 1 Revising Curriculum 2 Training on inclusive pedagogy 3 Technology integration, 4 Collaboration and partnership 5 Assessment and evaluation and role of teacher educators in preparing teachers for inclusive education is crucial, they empowers student teachers to create inclusive learning environment in classroom. Working together with parents, community members and stake holders we ensure that all students regardless of their abilities, disabilities and backgrounds have access high quality education and academic and social skills to succeed.

Key Words: *NEP 2020 and its importance, inclusive education, teacher education and digital era and need of digitalization of course content.*

Introduction:

NEP 2020, ministry of Human Resources Development, Government of India introduces policies and new era starts in Indian education system. In introduction of policy stately describes that this policy has reflection of the global education development agenda. This global education development agenda reflected in the Goal 4 (SDG4) of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, adopted by India in 2015. It ensures “ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all” by 2030. For

this goal entire education system will require to be changed, reorganized to foster learning. Teacher preparation for inclusive education included some key concepts is inclusive education, teacher education and technology for education. What NEP2020 said or consider about inclusive education, teacher education and technology for education.

Inclusive Education:

NEP2020 draw attention on the need for inclusive education. It involves providing equal opportunities for all students besides their abilities, disabilities or backgrounds. Principles of NEP 2020 policy provide a guideline for inclusive education.

Principles of NEP2020 Policy: Given by National Education Policy 2020 by Ministry of Human Resource Development, Government of India.

“The purpose of the education system is to develop good human beings capable of rational thought and action, possessing compassion and empathy, courage and resilience, scientific temper and creative imagination, with sound ethical moorings and values. It aims at producing engaged, productive, and contributing citizens for building an equitable, inclusive, and plural society as envisaged by our Constitution.”

Teacher Preparation:

NEP 2020 acknowledges the critical role of teachers in promoting inclusive education. It recommends that prepare teachers for inclusive education through training on inclusive education, diversity and equity.

Pre-service teacher training:

NEP2020 recommends that pre service teacher education programs should include courses on diversity, inclusion and special education. This will help teachers to develop necessary skills and techniques and attitudes to support students with special educational needs.

Collaboration and Partnership:

NEP2020 focuses on the importance of collaboration and partnership between schools, organizations and communities to help, to promote inclusive education. Teachers should motivate to work with special teachers, parents, community members and other stakeholders to support students with diverse needs.

Technology Integration:

NEP2020 emphasizes on the use of technology to support inclusive education. Teacher should be trained to use electronic/digital tools and resources to support students with diverse needs.

Assessment and evaluation:

Teacher training program should include training on assessment and evaluation methods. Implementing these recommendations teacher preparation programs can help prepare teachers to support inclusive education and promote equity and diversity in the classroom.

Implications for Teacher Preparation

The NEP2020 has remarkable implications for teacher preparation programs in India. Some of the key implications include,

Implications for Teacher Preparation

1 Revising Curriculum:

Revise present curriculum and include courses on diversity, equity and inclusive education.

2 Training on inclusive pedagogy:

Provide training on inclusive pedagogy and strategies for supporting students with diverse needs.

3 Technology integration:

Include training on technology integration for inclusive education.

4 Collaboration and partnership:

Encourage teachers for collaboration with parents, community members, and other stakeholders, special teachers to support students with diverse needs.

5 Assessment and evaluation:

Include training on inclusive assessment and evaluation methods.

What is the role of teacher educator?

Teacher educator plays crucial role to prepare pre service teacher for inclusive education. Following practices develop teacher students attitude towards inclusive education and develop skills to handle and help diverse needs student.

1 Model for inclusive practice:

Teacher educator show inclusive practices in their teaching to demonstrate what inclusive education looks like in present.

2 providing inclusive curriculum:

Teacher educator provide curriculum which includes knowledge of diversity needs, develop attitudes and skills for inclusive education.

3 Foster reflective practices:

To promote inclusive education teacher educator use reflective practices and also encourage student teachers to use reflect on their assumptions and practices.

Teacher Educator Plays Role for Inclusive Education.

4 Develop Competencies:

To promote inclusive education teacher educator provides opportunities to student teachers to learn about diverse culture, classroom environment and learning experiences.

5 Knowledge about Diversity:

To promote inclusive education teacher educator provides knowledge about diversities, types of disabilities, policies related to inclusive education, academic and social skills for inclusive

classroom.

6 provide opportunity at the time of lesson and internship:

To promote inclusive education teacher educator provides real world practice through lessons and internship program. Also through field visit provide opportunity to enhance knowledge about inclusive education

7 Encourage for collaboration:

To promote inclusive education teacher educator to encourage student teachers to collaborate with special teachers, colleagues and community members.

8 Develop Digital programs for inclusive education:

To promote inclusive education teacher educator should develop digital program on inclusive education for student teachers to provide real experience of integration of technology for inclusive classroom. Knowledge about assistive technology, digital accessibility and online learning platform.

In conclusion the NEP2020 recommended so many things and also provides remarkable implications for teacher preparation programs. Some of the key implications include,

1 Revising Curriculum 2 Training on inclusive pedagogy 3 Technology integration, 4 Collaboration and partnership 5 Assessment and evaluation and role of teacher educators in preparing teachers for inclusive education is crucial, they empowers student teachers to create inclusive learning environment in classroom. Working together with parents, community members and stake holders we ensure that all students regardless of their abilities, disabilities and backgrounds have access high quality education and academic and social skills to succeed.

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